

HOW TO ENCODE THE LITERARY FRENCH JOURNAL *COMMERCE* USING TEI

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Summary. This technical report aims to show all the steps followed to encode the literary journal *Commerce* according to the TEI P5 Guidelines. *Commerce* is a literary French journal founded in 1924 by Paul Valéry, Léon-Paul Fargue, and Valéry Larbaud, composed of 29 volumes published between 1924 and 1932. Each volume collects different literary material from various well-known and unknown writers as poems or novels which are all translations into French. In detail, with the paper we want to provide a guideline for the encoding of the volumes, showing all the tags and attributes which should be used and many examples taken from the XML of volumes number 5 and 6. This report is the result of work done in collaboration with the University of Pisa and the Institute for Computational Linguistics "A. Zampolli"- CNR Pisa.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. What is Commerce

Commerce is a literary French journal founded in 1924 by Paul Valéry, Léon-Paul Fargue, and Valéry Larbaud. It is composed of 29 volumes published between 1924 and 1932. Each volume collects different literary material from various well-known and unknown writers as poems or novels which are all translations into French. Therefore, each volume includes different articles which can be divided into chapters. Each volume has an index that shows the titles of the articles as well as the name of the authors, and a colophon at the end of it.

1.2. What is TEI

TEI is the acronym of the Text Encoding Initiative which develops standards for the representation of texts in digital form and it includes a set of Guidelines that specify encoding methods for machine-readable texts mainly in humanities, social science, and linguistics. With TEI, international tags are developed and can be used worldwide to encode texts of any kind and in any language. TEI uses XML language, therefore it requires a basic knowledge of software as *Oxygen*¹ in order to encode. The name of the tag is in blue and it is between chevrons (< >), attributes can be included inside the tag and are in orange and with an equal symbol. The specific value or information of the attribute is between quotation marks and it is red. Each tag is closed with the same name preceded by a slash.

1.3. The Project

Commerce encoding is part of the Commerce Numérique project run by the Institute for Computational Linguistics "C. Caetani" in Rome (OCR responsible F. Boschetti), the University of Pisa (Professor A. Sanna from the French Department as the general

¹ <https://www.oxygenxml.com/>

coordinator of the project), and the Institute for Computational Linguistics “A. Zampolli”-CNR Pisa, which is responsible for encoding (O. Nahli as encoding supervisor).

1.4. Presentation of the paper

With this paper, we are showing all the steps which must be followed to encode every single volume of the journal to make the encoding of the following volumes easier and similar. So far, only the first six volumes have been encoded, and this paper uses the encoding of volume number 6 (and volume number 5) as a guideline. We are going to show all the tags and attributes used with a theoretical explanation of them, taken from the *P5 Guidelines*², as well as a few examples taken from the XML of Commerce 5 and 6 (the latter was completed on December 2020). Lastly, for each example, a reference of the number of the XML line and sometimes the PDF page is provided. In fact, to encode each volume we used its correspondent PDF and the already generated XML text.

2. ENCODING CRITERIA

The encoding of Commerce is done volume by volume, and according to TEI guidelines, few tags are common in every text (found in every volume of the journal Commerce). The various tags used follow a hierarchical structure. In fact, in Commerce, we have:

```
5 ▾ <TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
6 ▶ <teiHeader> [47 lines]
54 ▶ <text> [4237 lines]
4292 </TEI>
```

<TEI> (*TEI document*) contains a single TEI-conformant document.

This tag is the first opened and it is closed at the very end of the entire text, as you can see below, the attribute's value refers to a link that shows the document we are encoding.

```
<TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
```

<teiHeader> (*TEI header*) supplies descriptive and declarative metadata associated with a digital resource or set of resources.

It is the second tag opened and it is closed right before the beginning of the actual text and the tag **<text>**.

<text> contains a single text of any kind, whether unitary or composite, for example, a poem or drama, a collection of essays, a novel, a dictionary, or a corpus sample.

We use this tag to indicate the entire text of the volume, from the very first word to the last one. In fact, the tag will be closed at the very end of the XML, right before the general tag **<TEI>**.

2.1. TeiHeader

² <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/index.html>

TeiHeader includes many other specific tags that express general information about the file as the project coordinator, the copyright, the encoding coordinator as well as the title, and so on and so forth. It is usually the same for all the volumes of Commerce. As you can see from the example, embedded in teiHeader we have:

```
7 ▾ | <fileDesc>
8 ▶ |   <titleStmt> [18 lines]
27 ▶ |   <publicationStmt> [4 lines]
32 ▶ |   <sourceDesc> [19 lines]
52 | </fileDesc>
```

<fileDesc> (*file description*) contains a full bibliographic description of an electronic file.

It is closed at the end of the teiHeader and it includes:

<titleStmt> (*title statement*) groups information about the title of the work and those responsible for it. (Paragraph 2.1.1.)

<publicationStmt> (*publication statement*) groups information concerning the publication or distribution of a document. (Paragraph 2.1.2.)

<sourceDesc> (*source description*) describes the source from which an electronic text was derived or generated, typically a bibliographic description or a phrase such as "born digital" for a text with no previous existence. (Paragraph 2.1.3.)

2.1.1. Title Statement

It includes more specific tags that give information about the title of the file and all the people responsible for the project:

```
8 ▾ | <titleStmt>
9 |   <title>Commerce 06</title>
10 ▶ |   <respStmt> [3 lines]
14 ▶ |   <respStmt> [3 lines]
18 ▶ |   <respStmt> [3 lines]
22 ▶ |   <respStmt> [3 lines]
26 | </titleStmt>
```

<title> *title of any kind*. As it is shown in the example it is "Commerce" and the number of the volume, in the example "06".

<respStmt> (*statement of responsibility*) supplies a statement of responsibility for the intellectual content of a text, edition, recording, or series, where the specialized elements for authors, editors, etc. do not suffice or do not apply. May also be used to encode information about individuals or organizations which have played a role in the production or distribution of a bibliographic work.

We use this tag to express the different roles mentioned before. In fact, we have 4 different tags and each of them is composed of more specific tags:

<resp> (*responsibility*) contains a phrase describing the nature of a person's responsibility or an organization's role in the production or distribution of a work.

In Commerce, we have a project coordinator, encoding supervisor, OCR, and TEI encoding.

<persName> (*personal name*) contains a proper noun or proper-noun phrase referring to a person, it includes forenames, surnames, honorifics, and added names:

<forename> contains a forename, given or baptismal name.

<surname> contains a family (inherited) name, as opposed to a given, baptismal, or nickname.

<affiliation> contains an informal description of a person's present or past affiliation with some organization, for example, an employer or sponsor.

In Commerce, we have the University of Pisa and CNR-ILC.

```
22 ▾ <respStmt>
23 <resp>TEI encoding</resp>
24 ▾ <persName><forename>Michela</forename> <surname>Bandini</surname>,
25 <affiliation>University of Pisa</affiliation></persName>
26 </respStmt>
```

2.1.2. Publication Statement

We have to make a statement about the copyright of the digital edition of the journal. For every volume we will have as follows:

```
27 ▾ <publicationStmt>
28 <p>Digital Edition by University of Pisa and CNR-ILC</p>
29 <p>All rights reversed to Caetani Foundation</p>
30 <p><date>2020</date></p>
31 </publicationStmt>
```

We personally suggest simply copying the content of volume 6 and pasting it in the volume that is being encoded, making sure to add the right year inside the **<date>** tag. (see point **A.** below)

2.1.3. Source Description

It is composed of another tag

```
32 ▾ <sourceDesc>
33 ▶ <biblStruct> [17 lines]
51 </sourceDesc>
```

<biblStruct> (*structured bibliographic citation*) contains a structured bibliographic citation, in which only bibliographic sub-elements appear and in order.

```

33 ▾      <biblStruct>
34 ▶      <monogr> [6 lines]
41 ▶      <series> [8 lines]
50      </biblStruct>

```

As we can see from the example, it includes the following tags:

A. **<monogr>** (*monographic level*) contains bibliographic elements describing an item (e.g. a book or journal) published as an independent item (i.e. as a separate physical object).

This tag includes:

<imprint> groups information relating to the publication or distribution of a bibliographic item.

Which gives information about the publisher, the location of the publication as well as the date. In fact, as we see from the following example, we need many other tags:

```

35 ▾      <imprint>
36 ▾      <publisher><persName><forename>L.</forename> <surname>Giraud-Badin</surname></persName>
37      <address><location><settlement>Paris</settlement></location></address></publisher>
38      <biblScope unit="volume">6</biblScope>
39      <date when="1925">Hiver 1925</date>
40      </imprint>

```

<publisher> provides the name of the organization responsible for the publication or distribution of the item.

Inside this tag we have more specific tags:

First of all, we need to give detailed information about the name, and surname of the publisher by using the following tags, already explained before:

<persName><forename><surname>.

Secondly, the information about the place of publication is marked with the following tags:

<address> contains a postal address, for example of a publisher, an organization, or an individual.

<location> defines the location of a place as a set of geographical coordinates, in terms of other named geo-political entities, or as an address.

<settlement> contains the name of a settlement such as a city, town or village.

Thirdly, we used the following tag with a specific attribute to specify the unit of our text: volume 6. In fact, we mark with this tag the number 6.

<biblScope unit="volume">

`<biblScope>` (*scope of bibliographic reference*) defines the scope of a bibliographic reference, for example as a list of page numbers, or a named subdivision of a larger work.

`unit=` identifies the unit of information conveyed by the element, e.g. columns, pages, volume, entry.

Lastly, the date of publication (Commerce 6 shows the season and the year) is marked with the next tag:

`<date when="1925">`

`<date>` contains a date in any format.

We use a specific attribute to refer to the year, which value is the year itself (in red).

`when=` supplies the value of the date or time in a standard form.

B. `<series>` (*series information*) contains information about the series in which a book or other bibliographic item has appeared.

```
41 | <series>
42 |   <title>Commerce</title>
43 |   <respStmt ana="editor">
44 |     <resp>publiés par les soins de</resp>
45 |     <persName><forename>Paul</forename> <surname>Valéry</surname></persName>
46 |     <persName><forename>Léon-Paul</forename> <surname>Fargue</surname></persName>
47 |     <persName><forename>Valery</forename> <surname>Larbaud</surname></persName>
48 |   </respStmt>
49 | </series>
```

Since each volume of Commerce is part of a series of 29 volumes, we use this tag together with its title “Commerce” (`<title>`) and the names of the editors which are Paul Valéry, Léon-Paul Fargue, and Valery Larbaud, as said before. (`<persName>`, `<forename>`, `<surname>`). The following tag shows, shows who are the different editors. In fact, the noun *editor* is between quotation marks and in red.

`<respStmt ana="editor">`

`ana=` (*analysis*) indicates one or more elements containing interpretations of the element on which the attribute appears.

2.2. Physical structure of the text

Every tag has to respect the physical structure of the journal, in fact, as we can see from the example below, this tag has a hierarchical structure and it includes other sections. This structure in XML perfectly mirrors the structure of the volume together with the typical components of a book. In fact, each volume has a title page, an index, the body of the text composed of various articles, and a colophon at the very end of it.

```

54 ▾ | <text>
55 ▶ | <front> [81 lines]
137 ▶ | <group> [4156 lines]
4294 ▶ | <back ana="colophon"> [14 lines]
4309 | </text>

```

<front> (*front matter*) contains any prefatory matter (headers, abstracts, title page, prefaces, dedications, etc.) found at the beginning of a document, before the main body. (See point **A**.)

<group> contains the body of a composite text, grouping together a sequence of distinct texts. (See point **B**.)

<back> (*back matter*) contains any appendixes, etc. following the main part of a text. (See point **H**.)

A. Title page and index

Those parts of the volume are included in the **<front>** tag that includes everything that goes from the very first page of the volume to the page which marks the beginning of the first article. As you can see, we included pages from x to 4. It embeds two tags, shown in detail in the next two paragraphs, which correspond to the title of the volume and the index. There is also a note on page 4. (Paragraph **2.4**.)

```

55 ▾ | <front>
56 | <milestone unit="page" n="x" />
57 | <milestone unit="page" n="1" />
58 ▶ | <titlePage> [16 lines]
75 |
76 | <milestone unit="page" n="2" />
77 |
78 | <milestone unit="page" n="3" />
79 ▶ | <listBibl type="index"> [46 lines]
126 |
127 | <milestone unit="page" n="4" />
128 ▶ | <note> [7 lines]
136 | </front>

```

<titlePage> (*title page*) contains the title page of a text, appearing within the front or back matter.

<listBibl> (*citation list*) contains a list of bibliographic citations of any kind.

Title Page

Page 2 of Commerce 6 (page 15 of the PDF), shows the title of the Volume. Lots of information are given, which is why this tag also includes others.

```

58 ▾ <titlePage>
59 ▶   <docTitle> [2 lines]
62 ▶   <docAuthor ana="editor"> [4 lines]
67 ▶   <docImprint> [6 lines]
74   </titlePage>

```

1. **<docTitle>** (*document title*) contains the title of a document, including all its constituents, as given on a title page.

In fact, the only part of the title is the name “COMMERCE” (see page 15 on the PDF), which is why we only used the following tag for it.

<titlePart type="main">

<titlePart> contains a subsection or division of the title of a work, as indicated on a title page.

With this particular tag, we used an attribute, as you can see from the example.

type= specifies the role of this subdivision of the title.

(*main* is between quotation marks, in red, and indicates that “Commerce” is the main title of the volume).

```

59 ▾ <docTitle>
60   <titlePart type="main">COMMERCE¶¶</titlePart>
61 </docTitle>

```

2. **<docAuthor>** (*document author*) contains the name of the author of the document, as given on the title page.

As you can see, we encoded every single name of the three authors of the journal by using the specific tags **<persName><forename><surname>**. We also inserted the attribute **ana=** in order to show that we are referring to the editor.

<docAuthor ana="editor">

```

62 ▾ <docAuthor ana="editor">
63   CAHIERS TRIMESTRIELS PUBLIÉS PAR¶
64   LES SOINS DE <persName><forename>PAUL</forename> <surname>VALÉRY</surname></persName>,¶
65   <persName><forename>LÉON-PAUL</forename> <surname>FARGUE</surname></persName>,
66   <persName><forename>VALÉRY</forename> <surname>LARBAUD</surname></persName>.¶
67 </docAuthor>

```

3. **<docImprint>** (*document imprint*) contains the imprint statement (place and date of publication, publisher name), as given (usually) at the foot of a title page.

```

67 ▾ <docImprint>
68     RÉDACTION ET ADMINISTRATION¶
69 ▾ <address>
70     <addrLine>160, RUE DU FAUBOURG SAINT-HONORÉ¶</addrLine>
71     <location><settlement>PARIS</settlement><district>--VIIIe¶</district></location></address>
72     <date when="1925">HIVER 1925</date> <gi>CAHIER</gi> <num>VI¶</num>
73 </docImprint>

```

As you can see from the example, the information given refers to the place of publication, the date of publication, and the number of the volume. We encoded the address by using those tags: `<address>` `<location>` `<settlement>` and another one to encode the number of the district (*arrondissement*).

`<district>` *contains the name of any kind of subdivision of a settlement, such as a parish, ward, or other administrative or geographic unit.*

We encoded the date with the `<date>` tag and the `when=` attribute (`<date when="n. anno">`). The name of the volume is encoded with a generic identifier and the number tag.

`<gi>` *(element name) contains the name (generic identifier) of an element.*

`<num>` *(number) contains a number, written in any form.*

Index

In Commerce 6 the index is on page 3 (17 in PDF). It shows the title “SOMMAIRE” encoded with the following tag:

`<head>` *(heading) contains any type of heading, for example, the title of a section, or the heading of a list, glossary, manuscript description, etc*

The heading tag is embedded in a more generic tag which marks the presence of a list:

`<listBibl>` *(citation list) contains a list of bibliographic citations of any kind.*

Since our list is an index, we inserted the generic attribute `type=` to show what kind of list we are referring to. In fact, the value of the attribute is `“index”`. >The list in the index is composed of the articles of Commerce 6. For each article it shows the author and right after it shows the title of it. Commerce 6 is composed of 11 articles, in fact, we can see 11 entries referring to the authors and 11 entries referring to the titles for a total of 22 entries. We encoded each author together with his article’s title with the following tag:

`<bibl>` *(bibliographic citation) contains a loosely-structured bibliographic citation of which the sub-components may or may not be explicitly tagged.*

The subcomponent are the author and the title. We encoded them with the already cited `<title>` tag and with a specific tag for the author’s name (we didn’t encode the name or surname).

<author> in a bibliographic reference, contains the name(s) of an author, personal or corporate, of a work.

```
79 ▾ <listBibl type="index">
80     <head>SOMMAIRE¶¶</head>
81 ▾   <bibl>
82     <author>LÉON-PAUL FARGUE¶¶</author>
83     <title>BANALITÉ¶¶</title>
84     </bibl>
85 ▾   <bibl>
86     <author>EDMOND TESTE¶¶</author>
87     <title>Extraits de son LOG BOOK¶¶</title>
88     </bibl>
```

B. Group of articles

Every single volume of Commerce is composed of various articles. Every volume is therefore a group of texts. **<group>** tag is opened right after the closure of the front tag, and it goes to the end of the text since it includes all the various articles of the volume. In Commerce 6, the very first article starts on page 5 (19, PDF). Before starting to encode the detailed parts of the article we need to encode the structure of the group, we did so by using the **<text>** tag which is opened on the first page of the article (usually the one that shows the title and the author's name) and it is closed on the last page of the article. We considered part of an article even the blank page that may appear in between the two articles, just to make things clearer and to include every single page in a specific article. For example, the second article of Commerce 6 "LOG BOOK" starts on page 13, where we can see the title, and it ends on the blank page 26 even if the signature of the author, Edmond Teste, is on page 25 (see page 39, PDF). In order to distinguish every article from the others, we used specific attributes listed as follows:

xml:id= (identifier) provides a unique identifier for the element bearing the attribute.

The value is composed by an **a**, the number of the volume (from 01 to 29), **-**, a **p** and the first page of the article, **-**, and another **p** and the last page of the article.

type= it classifies the text as an article, in fact the value of this attribute is **"article"**.

n= (label) an element, which is not necessarily unique within the document.

It allows us to indicate the article we are referring to. Its value in red and between quotation marks is: the name of the author, the title of the article (as they appear in the index).

```
<text xml:id="ax-py-pz" type="article" n="AUTHOR NAME,
ARTICLE TITLE">
```

```
137 ▾ <group>
138   <text xml:id="a06-p05-p12" type="article" n="LÉON-PAUL FARGUE, BANALITÉ"> [129 lines]
268   </text>
269   <text xml:id="a06-p13-p26" type="article" n="EDMOND TESTE, Extraits de son LOG BOOK"> [270 lines]
540   </text>
```

Embedded in every **<text>** tag we have another tag that is opened right after it and it is closed at the end of the entire article, right before the closing tag of **<text>**.

<body> (*text body*) contains the whole body of a single unitary text, excluding any front or back matter.

This tag includes all the words of the article, it is therefore closed at the end, right before the closure of the **<text>** tag.

After the encoding of the text id tag of the various articles, we can proceed with their encoding one by one, starting from the easiest in which there are no poems, chapters, dialogues, or particular aspects of the text. And then we can encode the rest. It is fundamental to start with one article and finish it, only right after you have finished it, you can move to the next one. Also, always use the same kind of tags and always focus on the same aspects of the text. For example, we decided to encode italics words or sentences with a specific tag and we did the same from article 1 to article 11. Make sure to not use too many tags which are redundant, TEI must be clear and easy to understand, there is no need to add too much information which is not fundamental for the final encoding of the journal. Last but not least, we only focused on generic linguistics aspects, we didn't take into consideration semantics (except the language used in poems or quotes).

As all said before, in commerce there 4 different kinds of articles:

- articles in prose with a unitary structure
- articles composed by different chapters or sections
- articles with poems
- articles with dialogues

Although, there are aspects of every single article that are the same regardless of its kind. In fact, every article has a title and a closer, which must be encoded with the same tags.

C. Title and closer in the article

Each article has a title and a signature, therefore we always start encoding those items, which are usually encoded in the same way in every article. For the title of the article we used the **<head>** tag (line 2757).

```
2753 <text xml:id="a06-p123-p138" type="article" n="CHARLES MAURON, POÈMES">
2754 <body>
2755 <milestone unit="page" n="123"/>
2756 <head>POÈMES¶</head>
2757
```

The name of the author usually appears at the end of the article, as a signature. We opted for an encoding that must be the same for every single article, and it is composed of various tags, as you can see from the example from the third article:

```
1768 céder pour que l'été prochain me rende¶</p>
1769 <l rend="hi" n="5">Dis patriis Italoque coelo !¶</l>
1770 <closer><signed><hi ana="uppercase"><persName><forename>VALERY</forename>
1771 <surname>LARBAUD</surname></persName>.¶</hi></signed></closer>
1772
1773 <milestone unit="page" n="80"/>
1774 </body>
1775 </text>
```

`<closer>` groups together salutations, datelines, and similar phrases appearing as a final group at the end of a division, especially of a letter.

`<signed>` (signature) contains the closing salutation, etc., appended to a foreword, dedicatory epistle, or other division of a text.

The name and the surname are encoded with `<persName><forename><surname>` tags.

The signature is always in uppercase, therefore we used the `<hi>` tag with its specific attribute (see paragraph 2.3.)

Also, it is possible to find an item right before the beginning of the text, encoded as follows:

`<epigraph>` contains a quotation, anonymous or attributed, appearing at the start or end of a section or on a title page.

Inside the epigraph can be found a dedication which is encoded with the `<p>` tag (see point D.) with the attribute `ana=` (the value refers to the fact that it is a dedication, written in red and between quotation marks)

`<p ana="dedication">`

```
138 <text xml:id="a06-p05-p12" type="article" n="LÉON-PAUL FARGUE, BANALITÉ">
139 <body>
140 <milestone unit="page" n="5"/>
141 <head>BANALITÉ¶¶</head>
142 <epigraph><p><hi>L'odeur du sureau me conseille¶
143 Le plus parfait oubli...¶</hi></p>
144 <p ana="dedication">A <persName><forename>LÉON</forename><surname> DELAMARCHE.¶¶</surname></persName></p></epigraph>
145
```

At the end of the text, after the `<closer>` it is possible to find a postscript, encoded as in the following example:

```
3865 thème le plus simple et le plus profond de la peinture :¶
3866 un peu de matière qui s'est mise à brûler.¶¶</p>
3867 <closer><signed><hi ana="uppercase"><persName><forename>JOSÉ</forename>
3868 <surname>ORTEGA Y GASSET</surname></persName>.¶¶</hi></signed></closer>
3869 <postscript><p>Traduit de l'Espagnol par¶
3870 <persName role="translator"><forename>JEAN</forename> <surname>BARUZI</surname></persName>.¶¶ </p></postscript>
3871
3872 <milestone unit="page" n="186"/>
3873 </body>
3874 </text>
```

`<postscript>` contains a postscript, e.g. to a letter.

It is important to take into consideration that sometimes the postscript includes other items as the reference to the translator of the text for which we used the `<personName>` with an attribute:

`role=` may be used to specify further information about the entity referenced by this name in the form of a set of whitespace-separated values, for example, the occupation of a person, or the status of a place.

In fact, its value is "translator".

```
<personName role="translator">
```

D. Articles in prose with a unitary structure

We suggest starting the encoding of the articles which show texts in prose, and that are not divided into chapters. In fact, it's fundamental to take a look at the following generic tag, used to encode paragraphs.

`<p>` (*paragraph*) marks paragraphs in prose.

We consider a paragraph a sentence or a group of more than one sentence. A paragraph does not necessary consider a sentence separated from another by a full stop, and also, we can have a paragraph that goes from one page to the following or even an entire page can be composed just by one long paragraph. To better understand, many examples are shown below.

1. One line/sentence paragraph (page 19, PDF page 33, XML line 386)

```
386 <p><hi>Sorte de prière particulière:¶</hi></p>
387 ▾ <p>« Je remercie cette injustice, cet affront qui m'a¶
388 « réveillé et dont la vive sensation m'a jeté loin de sa¶
389 « cause ridicule, me donnant aussi la force et le goût¶
390 « de ma pensée tellement qu'enfin mes travaux ont eu¶
391 « le bénéfice de ma colère; la recherche de mes lois¶
392 « a profité de l'incident. »¶</p>
```

2. Paragraph that finishes at a full stop (page 19, PDF page 33, XML lines from 387)

```
386 <p><hi>Sorte de prière particulière:¶</hi></p>
387 ▾ <p>« Je remercie cette injustice, cet affront qui m'a¶
388 « réveillé et dont la vive sensation m'a jeté loin de sa¶
389 « cause ridicule, me donnant aussi la force et le goût¶
390 « de ma pensée tellement qu'enfin mes travaux ont eu¶
391 « le bénéfice de ma colère; la recherche de mes lois¶
392 « a profité de l'incident. »¶</p>
```

3. Paragraph that doesn't finish at a full stop (page 31, PDF page 45, XML line 605)

As you can see, even if there is a full stop on line 605, the paragraph finishes on line 652.

602 <p>La strophe de Brébeuf et mon désir m'entraînaient¶
603 présent au haut de l'escalier et à travers les salles du¶
604 alais Carignan. Je veux revoir les Gaudenzio Ferrari¶
605 t revivifier mes souvenirs de quelques autres tableaux.¶
606 e dirai qu'il y avait beaucoup de monde chez le bar-¶
607 ier. Un quart d'heure aurait suffi, mais les Griffier,¶
608 uxquels je n'avais jamais fait attention, me retien-¶
609 ent à eux seuls dix minutes dans la salle de l'Ecole¶
610 ollandaise : ces vues d'un Londres ancien, pastoral,¶
611 ans fumées, avec une Tamise bleu d'azur portant des¶
612 ygues et bordée de prairies où on étend du linge (tout¶
613 ela à quelques centaines de mètres de la Tour) font¶
614 eaucoup rêver. Et il y a de l'imagination, d'une¶
615 spèce fantastique, dans les autres paysages de Grif-¶
616 er : une foule d'objets et de personnages disparates¶

4. Paragraph that starts on one page and finishes in the following. Page 172-173 (PDF page 177-178):

3558 <p>Rendons à nos pensées le fond dans lequel elles¶
3559 naquirent : présentons-les humblement comme des¶
3560 choses que nous trouvons en notre paysage, qui se¶
3561 lèvent devant nous, ni plus ni moins que ces ormes¶
3562 bordure de cette rivière, que ces fumées tremblantes¶
3563 sur les cheminées des villages. Ainsi firent les meilleurs¶
3564
3565 <milestone unit="page" n="173"/>
3566 <fw-- 173 -->¶
3567 parmi les hommes : Descartes n'oublie pas de nous¶
3568 conter que sa nouvelle méthode réformatrice de la¶
3569 science universelle s'offrit à lui un soir dans le poêle¶
3570 d'une maison germanique, et Platon, lorsqu'il nous¶
3571 découvre dans le <hi>Phèdre</hi> la science de l'amour qui est¶
3572 la science de la science, a soin de nous présenter So-¶
3573 crate et son ami dialoguant au milieu d'un jour cani-¶
3574 culaire au bord de l'Ilissos, sous la fraîcheur d'un haut¶
3575 platane sublime, tandis que sur leurs têtes les cigales¶
3576 helléniques versaient leur rumeur.¶</p>

E. Articles with chapters or sections

Some articles in the volume can be divided into sections or into chapters. For example, article number 5 of Commerce 6 was divided into 7 different sub-texts, while article number 4 was divided into 15 chapters. Whenever we have different texts inside the article (poems, novels, or chapters, etc.) we use the tag

<div> (text division) contains a subdivision of the front, body, or back of a text.

The tag is opened right before the beginning of the section and it is closed at the end of it. Taking into consideration article 4, we opened 15 different <div> tags and each of them was opened right before the number of the chapter and it was closed right at the end of it, right before the beginning of the next section. We decided to use the **type=** and **n=** attributes only for the chapter division since as said before, there was no need to add further redundant information. (For example, article 9 was composed of 2 different poems which are encoded in a specific way, the thing that will help us and the system understand that we are encoding poetic content, therefore adding the attribute would have been redundant. See point

F.) Also, we considered as redundant the attribute in the division of article 7, as you can see from the example below, we only used the general tag `<div>`.

```
2889 <div>
2890 <milestone unit="page" n="131"/>
2891 <fw>- 131 -¶¶</fw>
2892 <head><hi>LE STORE¶¶</hi></head>
2893 <p rend="hi">Où sont les Ombres familières, la fantaisie contournée¶¶
2894 de leurs gestes, leur liberté ironique d'irréalités, et ce bon¶¶
2895 goût qu'elles tiennent de n'avoir pas plus de poids que¶¶
2896 d'importance ? Derrière le store lumineux l'ombre du¶¶
2897 mur d'abord a disparu, puis celle des feuillages, d'un¶¶
2898 glissement oblique. Et voici maintenant que le vol d'une¶¶
2899 abeille, comme un papier noirci dans une flamme, bon-¶¶
2900 dit, hésite, s'abandonne, se dissout. Le cadre est vide.¶¶
2901 Plus rien n'existe du monde que l'éblouissement du ciel¶¶
2902 dévorateur.¶¶</p>
```

As shown in the next example, the values show what kind of division we are referring to (chapter) and the number of the chapter. (`<div type="chapter" n="x">`)

```
2194 <div type="chapter" n="6">
2195 <fw type="Num">VI¶¶</fw>
2196 <head>INFANDUM REGINA¶¶</head>
2197 <p><hi rend="uppercase">DOULEUR, MILICE.</hi> - Qui prend parti pour la¶¶
2198 douleur? qui peut aimer la douleur? qui peut s'y¶¶
2199 plaire ? Qui est assez fou pour le penser ? ou assez sot¶¶
2200 pour le dire? Ceux qui n'ont jamais souffert sans¶¶
2201 doute, les plus inertes des hommes et les plus insen-¶¶
2202 sibles, s'il en est seulement d'assez lourds pour ne pas¶¶
2203
```

Lastly, every single chapter came with a number and a title. For the number we used the `<fw>` tag (see paragraph 2.3.) with the `type=` attribute (value is `"Num"`, expressing that this item is a number). For the title we used the tag `<head>`.

`<fw type="Num">x¶¶</fw>`

F. Articles with poems

In Commerce³, there are two main kinds of poems:

- translated poems into French with no original version
- original poems in another language with a French translation

Sometimes the article shows the original version of the poem and the translations, but sometimes it doesn't. It is worth taking into consideration the structure of the poem. In the classical idea of poetry, poems are composed of verses that can be grouped in strophes according to rhymes or a number of verses, but according to the language of the original

³ For this section, examples from Commerce 5 and Commerce 6 are shown.

version, the structure of the poem does not mirror the typical structure of classical poetry. (we are going to talk about it later on). It is always mandatory to express the language of the poem while encoding, using a specific attribute.

Typical structure of poems

Usually, poems are divided into strophes which are composed of verses.

Strophes are encoded with the following tag:

```
<lg xml:id="lgx_yyy_z" xml:lang="fra">
```

<lg> (*line group*) contains one or more verse lines functioning as a formal unit, e.g. a stanza, refrain, verse paragraph, etc.

It requires many attributes:

xml:id= it's fundamental to identify the strophe, therefore it requires a value composed by:

lg number of the volume _ number of the page _ number of the strophe.

xml:lang= (*language*) indicates the language of the element content

its value is **"fra"** because it's a poem in French.

Verses are encoded with the following tag:

```
<l n="x">
```

<l> (*verse line*) contains a single, possibly incomplete, line of verse.

n= (*number*) gives a number for an element, which is not necessarily unique within the document.

It expresses the number of the line in the poem. In fact, as you can see from the example below, the verses are encoded with a number that follows a chronological order (same thing for the strophes). For example, if the poem has three different strophes they will be numbered 1, 2, and 3. Each strophe has five verses for a total of 15 verses, the verses will be numbered from 1 to 5 in Strophe 1, from 6 to 10 in Strophe 2, and from 11 to 15 in Strophe 3. We count the lines of the poem as a global part of the poem not as a part of the single strophe.

When the poem is in *italics*, the following tag is used:

```
<l rend="hi" n="x">
```

The only difference is the attribute **rend=** that refers to the highlighted aspect of the verse, in fact the value is **"hi"** (highlighted). (For further information, see paragraph 2.3.)

```

3901 <div>
3902 <milestone unit="page" n="189"/>
3903 <head><hi>NUIT ACCABLANTE¶¶</hi></head>
3904 <lg xml:id="lg6_189_1" xml:lang="fra">
3905 <l rend="hi" n="1">Il pleuvait. Mais elles ne se courbaient guère,¶¶</l>
3906 <l rend="hi" n="2">Les herbes au fond du sac d'orage,¶¶</l>
3907 <l rend="hi" n="3">La poussière avalait la pluie en pilules,¶¶</l>
3908 <l rend="hi" n="3">Le fer en poudre douce.¶¶</l>
3909 </lg>
3910 <space dim="vertical" unit="line" quantity="1"/>
3911 <lg xml:id="lg6_189_2" xml:lang="fra">
3912 <l rend="hi" n="4">Le hameau n'attendait point la guérison,¶¶</l>

```

We used the `<l rend="hi" n="x">` and `<lg xml:id="lgx_yyy_z" xml:lang="language">`

for verses used as quotes in prose articles. We also added the next tag:

`<quote type="indent-para">`

`<quote>` (*quotation*) contains a phrase or passage attributed by the narrator or author to some agency external to the text.

`type="indent-para"` refers to the fact that usually, all the quotes are intent paragraphs. as you can see from the example below.

```

560 <quote type="indent-para">
561 <lg xml:id="lg6_29_1" xml:lang="fra">
562 <l rend="hi" n="1">Je suis le ténébreux, le veuf, l'inconsolé,¶¶</l>
563 <l rend="hi" n="2"> Le prince d'Aquitaine à la tour abolie ?...¶¶</l></lg>
564 </quote>

```

The only difference is that when the quotation is made by only one verse, there was no need to add a `<lg>` tag.

```

606 <quote type="indent-para">
607 <l rend="hi" n="7">...D'une vie en tout temps superbe et malheureuse...¶¶</l>
608 </quote>

```

We used the same attributes and we followed the same steps as for general strophes and verses, pointing out the language used, and if the verses quoted are all part of the same poem (or song), the counting of the verses has to follow a chronological order, as for general poems.

1. TRANSLATED POEMS INTO FRENCH WITH NO ORIGINAL VERSION

Many poems in Commerce are French translations from poems of other languages (in Commerce 6, for example, we have poems translated from Russian, Arabic, and Turkish) and most of them are provided only in French without the original source, the only thing that let us understand that is translation is the closer at the end of the article that refers to the translation and the translator. In the example below, the poem in article 9 of Commerce 6 is a French translation of an original Russian poem. Only the French version is provided, and it mirrors the typical structure of poems with strophes composed of several verses. Therefore, the encoding is the same as in point 1.

```

3928 <head>DÉPART¶¶</head>
3929 ▾ <lg xml:id="lg6_191_1" xml:lang="fra">
3930 <l rend="hi" n="1">Murmure du sel qui s'égoutte,¶¶</l>
3931 <l rend="hi" n="2">Bruit de roues à peine marqué,¶¶</l>
3932 <l rend="hi" n="3">Tournant doucement le dos au port¶¶</l>
3933 <l rend="hi" n="4">Nous dépassons les entrepôts.¶¶</l>
3934 </lg>
3935 <space dim="vertical" unit="line" quantity="1"/>
3936 ▾ <lg xml:id="lg6_191_2" xml:lang="fra">
3937 <l rend="hi" n="5">Jaillissement, jaillissement, jaillissement sans échos.¶¶</l>
3938 <l rend="hi" n="6">Lancée sur la voie des gémisséments¶¶</l>
3939 <l rend="hi" n="7">La mer pâle et rose flamboie¶¶</l>
3940 <l rend="hi" n="8">Comme l'écorce des bouleaux.¶¶</l>
3941 </lg>

```

We used the already mentioned tag for strophes (`<lg xml:id="lgx_yyy_z" xml:lang="fra">`) and the same tag for verses in *italics* (`<l rend="hi" n="x">`).

The original version of the poem is not inserted in the volume, but it is fundamental to create a link with an external source.⁴ With TEI we can point to a document different from the current document but that can be stored in the same local filesystem of it, or in a different system.

In either case, the pointing can be done **absolutely** (using the entire address of the target document) or **relatively** (using an address relative to the current base URI in force). If there is no current URI base, we consider the base URI the one of the current document. Usually, the current base URI is the value of the `xml:base` attribute of the closest ancestor that has one.

`xml:base=` *provides a base URI reference with which applications can resolve relative URI references into absolute URI references.*

1. If the external source is available online, we can only use the following tag that points explicitly to a location on the Web:

`<ref target= "WEBSITE URI" >`

Yet, if the original version of the poem is a document stored locally in a file, we need to use the same tag but we need to provide an absolute URI reference. We use a different protocol:

`<ref target= "file: URI of the file" >`

2. As said before, we can also use a relative URI reference to point to a document. Therefore, we need to take into consideration that if no `xml:base` is specified, the location of the resource (the URI of the document) is determined relative to the resource indicated by the current base URI, which is the current document. Although, it is recommended to first change the current base URI by setting a new value for `xml:base` (setting as its value the

⁴ <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/it/html/SA.html#SAUR>

website where the resource is available). We insert the specific attribute in the `<div>` tag that refers to the poem we are encoding. Then we can use the `<ref>` tag.

`<div xml:base= "SOURCE-WEBSITE">`

`<ref target= "file: URI of the file" >`

Atypical structure of poems

It is fundamental to take into consideration that some poems are French adaptations of other languages and some of those languages do not have the same idea of poem as we are used to. For example, in many languages, such as Arabic, we don't have the same structure as classical poems, usually verses are hemistichs (half verses). Also, in the following example, a French translation of a poem written by a Turkish poet (Commerce 6, article number 7, chapter number 3) there are no strophes. Those aspects have to be taken into consideration while encoding. In fact, as happens for the poem on page 167 (PDF 181) there are no strophes and all the different verses (encoded with `<l>`) are part of only one group (`<lg xml:id="lgx_yyy_z" xml:lang="fra">`)

PDF - 181

```

3466 <head><hi>DEVR IDUP GELDIM DJIHANE...¶</hi></head>
3467 <lg xml:id="lg6_167_1" xml:lang="fra">
3468 <l rend="hi" n="1"><seg n="1">Tournant en cercle je suis venu au monde, pour que de¶</seg>
3469 <seg n="2" style="text-align:right">[nouveau j'y retourne.¶</seg></l>
3470 <l rend="hi" n="2"><seg n="1">J'ai habité le palais de ce corps, qu'il soit renversé et¶</seg>
3471 <seg n="2" style="text-align:right">[détruit ;¶</seg></l>
3472 <l rend="hi" n="3"><seg n="1">Après avoir vogué sur la mer omanienne de l'esprit dans¶</seg>
3473 <seg n="2" style="text-align:right">[la barque matérielle de mon corps,¶</seg></l>
3474 <l rend="hi" n="4"><seg n="1">Sur le rivage, que ce mien corps aille se consumer en¶</seg>
3475 <seg n="2" style="text-align:right">[humus ;¶</seg></l>

```

2. ORIGINAL POEMS IN ANOTHER LANGUAGE WITH A FRENCH TRANSLATION

This kind of poem is encoded with the same tag - with the same attributes - as the original poems in French (see point 1.), the only difference is the `xml:lang=` attribute which has a different value, in fact, it has to show the language used (for example it can be `"eng"` as English).

`<lg xml:id="lgx_yyy_z" xml:lang="original-language">`

As you can see from the example, the poem on Commerce 5, page 126 is in English. This original poem is followed by its translation into French. We use the `<lg>` tag since the poem is divided into strophes (composed of verses). Each verse is encoded with the `<l>` tag using `rend=` attribute and `n=` attribute.

```
2598 | <head>TRAIN--STOP : NIGHT¶</head>
2599 ▾ | <lg xml:id="lg5_128_1" xml:lang="eng">
2600 | <l rend="hi" n="1">The incoherent rushing of the train¶</l>
2601 | <l rend="hi" n="2">Dulls like a drugged pain¶</l>
2602 ▾ | <lg xml:id="lg5_128_2" xml:lang="eng">
2603 | <l rend="hi" n="3">Numbs¶</l>
2604 | <l rend="hi" n="4">To an ether throbbing of inaudible drums¶</l></lg>
2605 ▾ | <lg xml:id="lg5_128_3" xml:lang="eng">
2606 | <l rend="hi" n="5">Unfolds¶</l>
2607 | <l rend="hi" n="6">Hush within hush until the night witholds¶</l></lg>
2608 ▾ | <lg xml:id="lg5_128_4" xml:lang="eng">
2609 | <l rend="hi" n="7">Only its darkness.¶</l></lg>
2610 |
```

The fundamental difference between the first kind of poem in point A. is that here we have to use a new2 attribute. Every strophe of the original version (in our example, in English) corresponds to a specific strophe in French, and every time we encode strophes in the French version, we need to use the following tag:

`<lg corresp="#lgx_yyy_z" xml:lang="fra">`

Inside the tag `<lg>`, there are two different attributes, one refers to the language used, in fact, its value is `"fra"`, and the other one is

`corresp=` (*corresponds*) *points to elements that correspond to the current element in some way.*

The value of this attribute is the same (with a `#`) as the one of the `<lg>` tag of the original version. In fact, with this tag, we link the two strophes. See the example below of the French version of the English poem described above.

```
2631 | <head>ARRET D'UN TRAIN, LA NUIT¶</head>
2632 ▾ | <lg corresp="#lg5_128_1" xml:lang="fra">
2633 | <l rend="hi" n="1">La désordonnée et précipitée fureur¶</l>
2634 | <l rend="hi" n="2">S'apaise comme sous un narcotique une douleur¶</l></lg>
2635 ▾ | <lg corresp="#lg5_128_2" xml:lang="fra">
2636 | <l rend="hi" n="3">S'engourdit¶</l>
2637 | <l rend="hi" n="4">En un muet éther palpitant de tambours assourdis¶</l></lg>
2638 ▾ | <lg corresp="#lg5_128_3" xml:lang="fra">
2639 | <l rend="hi" n="5">S'épanouit</l><space dim="horizontal" unit="character" quantity="31"/><l rend="hi" n="6"><seg n="2">[à la nuit¶</seg>
2640 | <seg n="1">En des gouffres sans fin creusés de silence et ne laissant¶</seg></l></lg>
2641 ▾ | <lg corresp="#lg5_128_4" xml:lang="fra">
2642 | <l rend="hi" n="7">Que son obscurité.¶</l></lg>
2643 |
```

Peculiar graphic aspects of poems

It is worth noting that sometimes the verse of the poem does not finish at the end of the line but it finishes in the line after. As you can see from the example below many verses are too

long and don't fit in the line of the page, therefore they are put in the line under it and are marked with a square bracket.

PDF - 181

For example, “nouveau j’y retourne” is included in the verse number 1: “Tournant en cercle je suis venu au monde, pur que de” (the entire verse is: “Tournant en cercle je suis venu au monde, pur que de nouveau j’y retourne”). Whenever we see this graphic peculiarity, the encoding of the verse is a little bit more complicated, since we have to mark that those two lines are two parts of the same verse. The example below shows how the encoding has to be made:

```
3466 <head><hi>DEV R IDUP GELDIM DJIHANE...¶</hi></head>
3467 <lg xml:id="lg6_167_1" xml:lang="fra">
3468 <l rend="hi" n="1"><seg n="1">Tournant en cercle je suis venu au monde, pour que de¶</seg>
3469 <seg n="2" style="text-align:right">[nouveau j'y retourne.¶</seg></l>
```

`<l>` tag is opened at the beginning of the verse with its attributes `n=` and `rend=`, and it is closed at the end of the verse (in the second line). We use the following tag to mark the first part of the verse

`<seg n="1">`

`<seg>` (arbitrary segment) represents any segmentation of text below the chunk level.

the attribute refers to the number of the part, in fact, its value is "1" and it closed at the end of the first line which corresponds to the end of the first part of the verse. The second part of the verse is encoded as follows:

`<seg n="2" style="text-align:right">`

the attribute `n=` has "2" as its value since it refers to the second part of the verse, and the attribute `style=` refers to the alignment of the part of the verse, which is right as the value shows. This `<seg>` attribute is closed at the end of the second part of the verse, right before the closure of the `<l>` tag.

As you can see from the example before, it is possible that the second part of the verse is found in the line after which is composed by another verse. The idea is the same as before, the item preceded by a square bracket is the second part of the line above which is the first part of the entire verse. The only difference here is that we need to encode the space between the verse and the second part of the verse above (we do not refer to alignment as we did in the example before).

We encode the verse with `<l>` tag, part of the verse with `<seg>` tag and its `n=` attribute and we used the following tag to encode the space between the verse below and the second segment of the verse above:

`<space dim="horizontal" unit="character" quantity="x"/>`

the attributes used are:

dim= which corresponds to “horizontal”, in fact, the space refers to peculiar spaces between words, not between lines as said elsewhere.

unit= it refers to the unit we used to calculate the space, in this case, it is “character”. We consider as a number: letters, punctuations, and even blank spaces.

quantity= includes a number: the number of characters used to count the space.

« Parole claire, n'impliquant pas d'ambages
Que peut réclamer personne à personne ? Saisissez
Regardez ma vieillesse, mon bâton, ma sébile, [l'allusion

PDF - 171

```
3337 | <l rend="hi" n="12">« Parole claire, n'impliquant pas d'ambages¶</l>
3338 | <l rend="hi" n="13"><seg n="1">Que peut réclamer personne à personne ? Saisissez¶</seg></l>
3339 ▾ <l rend="hi" n="14">Regardez ma vieillesse, mon bâton, ma sébile,
3340 | <space dim="horizontal" unit="character" quantity="4"/><seg n="2">[l'allusion¶</seg></l>
```

H. Colophon

The colophon is a page usually found at the end of the volume that provides information about the publication of the book. It is not part of the group of articles in the volumes and it can't be considered just a simple text. In fact, it is marked with the `<back>` tag. Our volume is composed by:

- front matter with title page and index
- a group of articles
- back matter

The back matter in Commerce 6 just includes a colophon and three empty pages.

We encoded it with the following tags:

```
4294 ▾ <back ana="colophon">
4295 | <milestone unit="page" n="209"/>
4296 ▾ <p>Le gérant : RONALD DAVIS¶
4297 | PARIS. – SOC. GÉNÉR. D'IMPR. ET D'ÉDIT., 71, RUE DE RENNES. – 1925.¶</p>
4298 ▾ <p>Les manuscrits doivent être envoyés au Secrétariat de la¶
4299 | Rédaction : 160, rue du Faubourg--Saint--Honoré, Paris.¶
4300 | Ceux qui ne seront pas insérés seront retournés aux Auteurs¶
4301 | dans un délai de trois mois.¶</p>
4302 |
4303 | <milestone unit="page" n="210"/>
4304 |
4305 | <milestone unit="page" n="211"/>
4306 |
4307 | <milestone unit="page" n="212"/>
4308 | </back>
```

2.3. Typographical aspects of the text

Before starting the actual encoding of the body of the text, we have to take into consideration the typographical aspect of it: page numbers, spaces, font of words, and illustrations. In the following paragraphs, we will show give details about them, by showing the order we followed in Commerce 6.

2.3.1. Page numbers

Before starting everything else, we have to number every single page of the text by using specific tags. Every volume is made of a range of 200-300 pages each, some of them come with a number on top of the page (usually in the middle) while others do not. Usually, the already generated xml text provides the page number as well as the tag used. Although sometimes the tag of the page number or the page number is missing because of previous mistakes, that is why we need to start looking at the PDF provided to make sure all the page numbers, as well as all the words, paragraphs, and chapters, are correctly generated. By comparing the PDF and the XML, we can detect which numbers are missing and therefore we can add them by simply typing them or copying them from a previously already provided number. (Volume 6 came with many missing numbers, around 30, and only one missing paragraph: page 153 was typed by the TEI encoding). If the first pages of the text do not have numbers, we can give it to them by simply counting down starting from the first page which shows a number in the PDF. For example, in Commerce 6, we started counting from page 8. By doing so, we were able to have the exact tag even for all the pages before that: 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1. In Commerce 6 there is also an extra page at the beginning of the text, which we counted as x.

The tag used for every single page is the following:

`<milestone />` marks a boundary point separating any kind of section of a text. . It is used with two different attributes:

`unit=` provides a conventional name for the kind of section changing at this milestone.

In Commerce is “page”.

`n=` (number) gives a number (or other label) for an element, which is not necessarily unique within the document.

It refers to the page number itself, shown between quotation marks.

`<milestone unit="page" n="x"/>`

The number shown in the PDF is as follows.

PDF - page 22

It must be encoded with the tag:

`<fw>` (forme work) contains a running head (e.g. a header, footer), catchword, or similar material appearing on the current page.

```
170 | <milestone unit="page" n="8"/>
171 | <fw>- 8 -¶</fw>
```

2.3.2. Illustrations

Commerce 6 had many asterisks (*) which divide different paragraphs, sections, or chapters.

PDF - page 21

We encoded them with the tag `<fw>` but using the following attribute:

`type=` classifies the material encoded according to some useful typology. Specifying what we are referring to, a figure.

```
<fw type="figure">*</fw>
```

```
165 | <fw type="figure">*¶
166 | * *¶</fw>
```

2.3.3. Space

We marked the atypical space we have between lines. As you can see from the example in the following picture, sometimes paragraphs or sections are divided by a space that corresponds to one or more missing lines. We didn't take into consideration spaces between heads, titles, chapter numbers, closers, signatures, or figures. We only took into consideration spaces between the body of the text.

PDF - page 124

`<space/>` indicates the location of a significant space in the text.

This tag is inserted right where the space is. It is used with three different attributes:

`dim=` (dimension) indicates whether the space is horizontal or vertical. In this case, we insert the value `"vertical"` since the space refers to lines, which are one after the other in a vertical orientation.

`unit=` names the unit used for the measurement. We used the value `"line"`.

quantity= specifies the length in the units specified.

The values is a number, which correspond to the number of line “missing” in the space.

```
<space dim="vertical" unit="line" quantity="x"/>
```

```
2456 | nulle qu'une pensée sans conscience. Prendre cons-¶
2457 | science, enfin, tout est là.¶</p>
2458 |     <space dim="vertical" unit="line" quantity="1"/>
2459 | <p>La vie intérieure détermine des formes qui ne sont¶
2460 | qu'à elle. La grande poésie et la grande pensée n'ont¶
2461 | pas d'autre origine : la même nécessité s'exprime en¶
```

2.3.4. Numbers at the end of the page

Some pages have a little number on the bottom right, in Commerce 6 we have 12 little numbers (from 2 to 13). This number is usually printed on the first page of each spreadsheet used for printing, this page is usually folded four, eight, or sixteen times depending on the book format, that is why those numbers appear just in a few pages of the volumes and are in chronological order.

PDF - page 31

Since they just appear as little numbers at the end of the page, not included in any paragraph, they are marked with the **<fw>** tag, which comes with two different attributes:

type= classifies the material encoded according to some useful typology. “Num” as the value is used to refer to the fact that it is a number.

place= specifies where this item is placed. The value is **“bot-right”**, since the number is on the bottom right of the page.

```
<fw type="Num" place="bot-right">X</fw>
```

```
348 | tances de l'eau.¶</p>
349 | <fw type="Num" place="bot-right">2¶</fw>
```

2.3.5. Highlighted items

As mentioned before, we decided to encode a few aspects of the text, including letters, words, or sentences which are distinguished from the others. We took into consideration words in *italics* and words in UPPERCASE. For all those aspects we used the tag.

<hi> (*highlighted*) marks a word or phrase as graphically distinct from the surrounding text.

Whenever it was in *italics*, we simply used the tag without any attributes as you can see from the next example.

— 36 —

de Samuel Butler qui a dû souvent parcourir ces rues
et faire ce chemin du Musée à l'hôtel qui est justement
l'hôtel dont il a fait l'éloge dans *Alps and Sanctuaries*,
et tout notre passé, et ce que nous pouvons entrevoir
de notre avenir : notre route vers Orta et le lac
Majeur...

PDF – 50

```
715 <milestone unit="page" n="36"/>
716 <fw>- 36 -</fw>¶
717 de Samuel Butler qui a dû souvent parcourir ces rues¶
718 et faire ce chemin du Musée à l'hôtel qui est justement¶
719 l'hôtel dont il a fait l'éloge dans <hi>Alps and Sanctuaries</hi>,¶
720 et tout notre passé, et ce que nous pouvons entrevoir¶
721 de notre avenir : notre route vers Orta et le lac¶
722 Majeur...¶</p>
```

If the entire text was in italics, for example article number 1, we used the `<p>` tag with a specific attribute.

rend= (*rendition*) indicates how the element in question was rendered or presented in the source text. In fact, its value is: **"hi"**, which stands for highlighted. (`<p rend="hi">`)

Ma mère, je te regardais glisser dans cette chambre, inaltérable et douce, exilée du bonheur, dans la grande lumière qui venait du canal, au milieu des objets familiers dont nous connaissons toutes les petites figures, toutes les manies de petits bonshommes, et tu essayais de chanter.

Moi je portais ce cœur trop lourd, ce cœur faible et présomptueux, comme un écolier qui court avec un pain plus grand que lui.

Nous foulions tous les trois le champ des souvenirs, avec un vieil ami qui parlait dans sa pipe.

Appuyons-nous encore à ce mur bleuisant que la persienne ennuie.

Buvons encore à la fenêtre où nous avons tant de fois goûté le sel des larmes.

*
**

La girouette qui défend ce toit chargé de filets noirs plaignait sa fumée rudement enlevée par le vent du canal.

PDF – page 21

```

148 <milestone unit="page" n="7"/>
149 <p rend="hi">Ma mère, je te regardais glisser dans cette chambre,
150 inaltérable et douce, exilée du bonheur, dans la grande
151 lumière qui venait du canal, au milieu des objets familiers
152 liers dont nous connaissons toutes les petites figures,
153 toutes les manies de petits bonshommes, et tu essayais de
154 chanter.</p>
155 <p rend="hi">Moi je portais ce cœur trop lourd, ce cœur faible et
156 présomptueux, comme un écolier qui court avec un pain
157 plus grand que lui.</p>
158 <p rend="hi">Nous foulions tous les trois le champ des souvenirs,
159 avec un vieil ami qui parlait dans sa pipe.
160 Appuyons-nous encore à ce mur bleuisant que la
161 persienne ennue.</p>
162 <p rend="hi">Buvons encore à la fenêtre ou nous avons tant de
163 fois goûté le sel des larmes.</p>
164 <fw type="figure">*</fw>
165 * *</fw>
166 <p rend="hi">La girouette qui défend ce toit chargé de filets noirs
167 plaignait sa fumée rudement enlevée par le vent du canal.</p>
168

```

UPPERCASE words are encoded with the `<hi>` tag with the `rend=` attribute. Its values is: `"uppercase"`. (`<hi rend="uppercase">`)

PDF – page 110

```

2113 <div type="chapter" n="5">
2114 <fw type="Num">V</fw>
2115 <p><hi rend="uppercase">TOUTE</hi> métaphysique est faite pour porter une
2116 mathématique; et toute mathématique pour exprimer une physique. Il faut un système de l'esprit pour
2117 soutenir le nombre ; et le nombre porte le système de
2118

```

In Commerce, it is also possible to have initials, a letter at the beginning of the text - or of the chapter, article, or section - that is usually bigger than the others⁵.

PDF – page 97

2.4. Annotations

A. In Commerce we encoded all the annotations made by the editors or made by the authors in every article. In fact, we always used the same tag but with specific attributes according to the different kinds of annotation. If the annotation is general, and it is made at

⁵ Need to figure out how to encode CAPILETTRE.

the beginning or at the end of the text to express information about the text itself we use the general tag

`<note>` contains a note or annotation.

In Commerce 6, this kind of annotation is found at the beginning of the text (embedded into `<front>` as mentioned in paragraph 2.2.) on pages 4, and 18 on the PDF.

```
128 | <note>
129 |     IL A ÉTÉ TIRÉ DE CE CAHIER 2.850 EXEMPLAIRES¶
130 | DONT 100 EXEMPLAIRES SUR HOLLANDE VAN¶
131 | GELDER NUMÉROTÉS DE 1 A 100, 250 EXEMPLAIRES¶
132 | SUR PUR FIL LAFUMA NUMÉROTÉS DE 101 A 350,¶
133 | ET 2.500 EXEMPLAIRES SUR ALFA NUMÉROTÉS¶
134 | DE 351 A 2850.¶
135 | N° 27¶ </note>
```

B. We used this tag also for short notes inserted inside the article in which an observation or information is concretized by the author of it. It is usually made in reference to the content of the article, how or where it was written, and so on and so forth. This kind of note in Commerce 6 appears at the beginning of the text usually in brackets, in italics (it is possible to use the tag `<hi>`), and sometimes the note is aligned on the right part of the page, therefore it is possible to use the tag `<hi>` and use the following attribute

`style=` contains an expression in some formal style definition language that defines the rendering or presentation used for this element in the source text. In fact, its value is `"text-align:right"` in reference to the alignment of the text, on the right, indeed. For clearness, see the example below. (`<note style="text-align:right">`)

```
550 | <note style="text-align:right"><hi>( Ecrit à Orta Novarese.)¶</hi></note>
551 | <p>Chanter ou déclamer quelque chose de triste lors-¶
552 | qu'on est plein de contentement a la vertu de parfaire¶
553 | notre joie. A une des heures les plus belles de ma jeu-¶
554 | nesse, quand j'allais m'embarquer pour le Pirée et que¶
555 | le bateau partait demain, quels rythmes murmurés¶
556 | dans le bruit de la foule et des voitures, aux Allées de¶
557 | Meilhan, rue de Noailles, à la Cannebière, exprimèrent¶
558 | l'ivresse dont j'étais rempli, sinon :¶</p>
```

C. The last kind of note we found in Commerce 6 is like a complementary annotation of an item in the text (word, sentence, quotation, etc.) of a documentary or explanatory nature. This kind of note usually appears as typographically distinct from the text, for example as a footnote introduced with a number. Usually, with this kind of note, there are two numbers, one in the text and one at the end of the page before the note which links the note itself to the word or sentence in the text (the number of the text refers to the number of the note). The encoding of these notes is a little bit complicated since we have to express the reference function of the number. In fact, we encode the number on the text with the following tag:

```
<ref xml:id="rX-Y" target="#nX-Y" type="noteAnchor">
(x)</ref>
```

`<ref>` (reference) defines a reference to another location, possibly modified by additional text or comment.

We need three different attributes:

xml:id= its value is composed by an **r** (as in reference), a number (the number of the note), - and another number (the number of the page).

target= specifies the destination of the reference by supplying one or more URI References.

In fact, its value is composed of a **#** , an **n** (as in note), a number (the number of the note), - and another number (the number of the page where the note appears).

type= its value is "**noteAnchor**" which refers to what the number is, an element that marks the reference position of the note. In fact, we tag with **<ref>** the number that appears in the text since it is the anchor, which is necessary to indicate the reference position.

The note itself is encoded with the **<note>** tag with specific attributes. (**<note xml:id="nX-Y" type="footnote">**(x)**<ref target="#rX-Y">**). The tag is opened right before the number and it is closed at the end of the note. The attributes are:

xml:id= its value is composed of an **n** (as in note), a number (the number of the note), - , and another number (the number of the page).

type= its value is "**footnote**" which refers to what the number is or, to be more precise, what it precedes, a footnote.

The number that precedes the note is encoded with **<ref>** and the **target=** attributes. Its value is composed of a **#** , an **r** (as in reference), a number (the number of the note), - and another number (the number of the page where the note appears). It must be the same value as the target attribute of the **<ref>** tag of the number that appears in the text so that the reference and the link between the two numbers (the item in the text and the note) is encoded.

<ref target="#rX-Y">

```
3418 <l rend="hi" n="1">Il se prépare à me tuer, - mais en Lui je suis extasié <ref xml:id="r1-162" target="#n1-162" type="noteAnchor"> (I)</ref></l>
3419 <l rend="hi" n="2">Dans ce geste où IL tire son épée, - ah! quelle beauté ! >></l></lg>
3420 <p>Cette idée, que typifie le verset (où le pharaon
3421 s'écrie) : « Coupez-leur mains et pieds, en sens alterné »</p>
3422 <note xml:id="n1-162" type="footnote"><ref target="#r1-162">(I)</ref><p>Ce distique quelques pages plus loin est explicitement attribué
3423 à Halladj par Ahmad Ghazali : « A l'heure où son Bien-Aimé a déployé
3424 le tapis de l'exécution, et où l'amant va mourir, Sa beauté l'extasie et il
3425 s'écrie : Il se prépare à me tuer... » Cette entrée en scène déjà légendaire
3426 du « martyr de Bagdad », du « saint » par excellence du mysticisme musul-
3427 man, était à souligner.</p></note>
```

3. CONCLUSIONS

This paper is made to simplify the future encoding of the volumes in the French journal Commerce, and it is meant to be used as guidelines to encode the entire journal. By now only the first six volumes are encoded, but we are planning on finishing the encoding using the general tags we used in Commerce 6 so that we can focus on the same aspects from volume 1 to volume 29. We took into consideration mainly the structure of the volume and how it must be encoded. The encoding must mirror the structure of the journal, therefore we thought that

focusing on typography and general tags was the most important thing to do (at this step of the project). We didn't focus on semantic aspects of the text, yet we only took into consideration the language used in poems since Commerce is a multilingual literary journal. Apart from the structure of the volume (that is mostly the same in every single volume of the journal), we wanted to show what kinds of articles are inserted in the volume. Therefore, particular attention was given to the articles made of poems. In the next future, we intend to focus on the encoding of poems in languages that do not have a typical metric structure like Arabic.